

Expansion of the Invasive Moon Crab *Matuta victor* in Turkish Waters: A New Record from Mersin

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Research Article

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Abstract

In this study, a single female specimen of the moon crab, *Matuta victor* (Fabricius, 1781), was recorded in Erdemli, Akkum (Mersin) in May 2024. *M. victor* is a marine decapod species whose recent sightings in different regions and expanding distribution are increasingly reported. This paper mainly confirms its presence in Erdemli, Akkum (Mersin) and shares concerns about the possible ecological and economic impacts of its expanding presence along the Mediterranean coast of Turkey. The expanding distribution of *M. victor* suggests an urgent need to assess the invasion process of the species and its impact on the local ecosystem, as well as for studies based on continuous monitoring to understand the ecological impact of this species and develop effective management strategies. This study also provides distribution information on newly introduced species for conservation efforts to protect the local marine ecosystem.

Keywords: Moon crab, *matutidae*, distribution, expansion, Gulf of Mersin, Türkiye

Introduction

Crustaceans are the second most abundant group among non-indigenous species (NIS) in the Mediterranean Sea. More than 90 species of these crustaceans belong to the order Decapoda.

Approximately 400 decapod species have been reported from the Mediterranean Sea, of which 24% are non-indigenous species (Coll et al., 2010; Galil et al., 2015). The most recent records of Decapods in the Mediterranean Sea include the moon crab, *Matuta victor* (Fabricius, 1781), originating from the Indo-Pacific and the Red Sea (Dailianis et al., 2016; Kondylatos et al., 2018).

The moon crab, *Matuta victor* (Fabricius, 1781), is native to the Indo-Pacific region, which includes the Gulf of Suez, Red Sea, Gulf of Oman, Arabian Sea, East Africa, Comoros, Madagascar, India, the Andaman Sea, Malaysia, Indonesia, the South China Sea, Japan, New Caledonia, Australia, the New Hebrides, Taiwan, the southern coast of Thailand, and the western and eastern coasts of Java (Ng, 1998; Ng and Huang, 1997; Ng et al., 2001; Fazrul et al., 2015; Hanim et al., 2023; Syuhada, 2024).

In the Mediterranean, *M. victor* was first reported from Haifa (Israel) in 2012 (Galil & Mendelson, 2013). It was then reported from Batroun (Lebanon) in 2013, from Tyr and Saida (Lebanon) in 2014 (Crocetta & Bariche, 2015), from Antalya Bay (Turkey) in 2015 (Gokoglu et al., 2016), from Muğla, İztuzu Beach (Turkey) in 2017 (Ateş et al., 2017), from the Syrian coast in 2017 (Zeini & Hasan, 2017), from Greek waters (Rhodes Island, Greece) in 2018 (Kondylatos et al., 2018), and from the Iskenderun coast (Turkey) in 2019 (Yeşilyurt et al., 2019) and Karataş coast (Adana, Turkey) in 2020 (Türeli, 2023).

This paper reports that the most recent record of *M. victor* along the Turkish coast is from the Gulf of Mersin (Erdemli, Akkum). Moreover, this paper confirms the presence of Moon Crab in Erdemli, Akkum (Mersin), and shares concerns about the possible ecological and economic impacts of its expanding presence along the Mediterranean coast of Türkiye.

Material and Methods

A female moon crab, *M. victor*, was found during a survey in Mersin Bay in May 2024. Figure 1 shows the location on the map of the Erdemli-Akkum coast where the specimen was collected. The identification of the *M. victor* was performed according to Galil and Clark (1994), Galil and Mendelson (2013), and Behera et al. (2018). The carapace length, width, and body weight of the moon crab were quantified using a digital caliper (to the nearest mm) and a digital balance (g). The specimen was recorded at the Marine Life Museum of Mersin University with catalog number MEUDC-24-13-015 and preserved in ethanol. Species identification was based on morphological characteristics.

Figure 1. Location where specimens of the *Matuta victor* were collected in Mersin Bay.

Results

A female *M. victor* specimen had a carapace length (CL) of 23.32 mm and a carapace width (CW) of 38.35 mm (Figure 2). The carapace is subcircular, bearing two long, well-developed lateral spines. Cephalopod is subequal; the pollex is slightly shorter than the dactylus. The dactylus contains a clear milled ridge on the outer surface, having two spines in males. However, the milled ridge is absent in females, and the spine is three. Color: The male specimen appears yellowish or light greenish with numerous small and evenly scattered black dots on the carapace.

Figure 2. a) Ventral view of female individual of *Matuta victor*, b) Dorsal view of female individual of *Matuta victor* CL: 23.32 mm, CW: 38.35 mm.

Discussion

In the present study, a single female specimen of *M. victor* was reported from Erdemli, Akkum (Mersin). This species prefers sandy areas between 0 and 20 m depth and is commonly caught by net,

hand, or beach seines (Ng, 1998; Ng and Huang, 1997). Bellwood (2002) noted that Matutid crabs can quickly bury themselves in sand. *M. victor* is considered a carnivorous Indo-Pacific species. It feeds mainly on crustaceans and molluscs such as anomurans, bivalves and snails (Perez and Bellwood, 1998).

The moon crab is a marine predatory decapod species whose recent sightings in various regions and expanding distribution are increasingly being reported. Known as an aggressive and slow predator of moving benthic invertebrates, *M. victor* has developed robust populations in the most diverse coastal environments, such as the southeastern Mediterranean Sea and Haifa Bay in northern Israel (Dailianis et al., 2016).

Recently, Türeli (2023) conducted a biological analysis of the invasive moon crab *Matuta victor* along the Karataş coast of Adana, Turkey, and the study provided important insights into the behavior and ecological impacts of the crab. The invasive nature and adaptability of the moon crab demonstrate its potential to alter the habitats of native species, which would require comprehensive research on its ecological impacts. Zviely et al. (2021) suggest that the presence of *M. victor* will disrupt the local ecosystem, particularly in sandy beaches and coastal water habitats.

The recent occurrence of *M. victor* in Erdemli Akkum (Mersin) is the latest record of its expanding distribution, and there are concerns about its potential impact on local biodiversity. *M. victor* is a newly arrived species in the Mediterranean, and it has recently settled and established a population in Mersin Bay due to suitable environmental conditions. The expanding distribution of *M. victor* suggests that there is an urgent need to try to assess the invasion process of the crab species. It is necessary to conduct studies based on continuous monitoring to evaluate the invasion process of this crab species. It is also important to understand the invasion pathway and biology of alien species in the surrounding ecosystem to mitigate the ecological impact of this species and to develop effective management strategies (Turan et al., 2024; Uyan et al., 2024).

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Author Contributions

Authors performed all the experiments and drafted the main manuscript text. Authors reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Ethical Approval Statements

Local Ethics Committee Approval was not obtained because experimental animals were not used in this study.

Data Availability Statement

The data used in the present study are available upon request from the corresponding author.

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